

Actual vs Predicted (TempVariance)

Standardized Residuals (TempVariance)

Partial Regression Plot (TempVariance)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.7918$$

Interpretation:

- 1 = positive autocorrelation**
- 2 = no autocorrelation**
- 4 = negative autocorrelation**

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 1.1084

p-value: 0.2924

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 2.2779

df: 2

p-value: 0.3202

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (TempVariance)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – TempVariance

